

Human Capital and Entrepreneurial Development in Lagos State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigates the influence of human capital on entrepreneurial development in Lagos State, Nigeria, focusing on the roles of education, work experience, and skills. Grounded in the Resource-Based View and Human Capital Theory, it addresses a critical knowledge gap on how these factors drive entrepreneurial growth. A descriptive research design was adopted, targeting 1,500 entrepreneurs across Lagos State's three senatorial districts. The research instruments, validated through a pilot study involving 150 SMEs in Ibadan, achieved a reliability coefficient of 0.83. Data were analysed using hierarchical regression. The results reveal a strong positive relationship between entrepreneurial development and human capital components. Education contributed a modest but significant proportion to entrepreneurial success ($R^2 = 0.008$), while work experience and skills accounted for a substantial predictive power ($R^2 = 0.941$). These findings underscore the vital role of human capital in fostering entrepreneurship, indicating that individuals with higher education, relevant experience, and advanced skills are better positioned to succeed in entrepreneurial ventures. The study concludes that human capital is a pivotal determinant of entrepreneurial development in Lagos State. To enhance entrepreneurship and drive economic growth, investments in education, skill acquisition, and work experience are essential. Policymakers, educational institutions, and private organisations must collaborate to implement policies and programmes that prioritise human capital development as a strategic driver of entrepreneurship and sustainable economic progress.

Keywords: entrepreneurial development, human capital, skill acquisition

Word Count: 220

Introduction

Human capital, which encompasses elements such as education, skills, health, and experience, is widely recognised as a key driver of economic growth and development. Investments in human capital are essential for boosting global productivity and creativity, which in turn fosters entrepreneurial ventures. According to the World Bank (2018), countries that invest in human capital are more likely to experience economic growth, as a skilled workforce is better equipped to leverage technology and innovate business practices. In countries like the United States and Germany, the focus on education and continuous skill development has been pivotal in creating a robust economic environment. The United States, for example, has cultivated a culture of innovation, supported by high educational standards and infrastructure that promotes research and development.

The Global Entrepreneurship Index (GEI) highlights that human capital attributes, such as entrepreneurial education and training, play a crucial role in the success of new businesses (Ács et al., 2017). Germany's dual education system, which integrates vocational training with academic education, has been essential in producing a highly skilled workforce that supports the country's thriving small and medium-sized enterprise (SME) sector (Federal Ministry of Education and Research, 2020). The importance of human capital in promoting entrepreneurial development is increasingly recognised, particularly in the African context. For instance, in South Africa and Kenya, investments in education and skills development have been closely tied to entrepreneurial growth. South Africa's National Development Plan 2030 emphasizes the need for a highly educated workforce to support entrepreneurship and innovation (South African Government, 2012; Oyedokun & Somoye, 2018c). The country has made strides in improving access to higher education and vocational training, leading to a surge in technological startups and innovative firms, especially in cities like Johannesburg and Cape Town.

Similarly, Kenya has leveraged digital literacy and mobile technologies to boost entrepreneurship. The government's Vision 2030 strategy prioritises ICT skill development and digital entrepreneurship (Kenya Vision 2030, 2020). The success of M-Pesa, a mobile money platform, exemplifies the potential of integrating technology with business ventures. M-Pesa has provided financial services to individuals without access to traditional banking, thereby fostering the growth of digital businesses and demonstrating how targeted human resource development can drive entrepreneurial initiatives.

The relationship between human capital and entrepreneurial development in Nigeria, Africa's largest economy, is both complex and multifaceted. Nigeria's youthful population offers both opportunities and challenges for entrepreneurial growth. Despite its economic potential, Nigeria faces significant human capital constraints, including limited access to quality education, inadequate healthcare, and insufficient vocational training. According to the National Bureau of Statistics (2021), the country grapples with high unemployment rates, especially among young people. This situation highlights the critical need for effective human capital development to stimulate entrepreneurship. The Nigerian government recognizes the role of human capital in fostering economic diversification and reducing dependence on oil revenue. Initiatives such as the Youth Entrepreneurship Support (YES) Programme and the National Youth Service Corps (NYSC) Skills Acquisition and Entrepreneurship Development (SAED) programme aim to equip young Nigerians with the skills necessary to create and sustain businesses (Oyedokun & Adeyemi, 2019; Central Bank of Nigeria, 2019).

However, the success of these programmes is hampered by challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, legal barriers, and limited access to financial resources. Empirical research indicates that factors such as education, work experience, skills, health, and training are critical to the success of entrepreneurs in Nigeria. A 2019 study by the African Development Bank found that individuals with higher education and prior work experience are more likely to succeed in entrepreneurship. Furthermore, ongoing training and development programs have been linked to improved business performance and innovation in Nigeria's SMEs (World Bank, 2020; Oyedokun, & Somoye, 2018a).

Despite the availability of training, research has shown that the educational background, work experience, and skills of many entrepreneurs in Nigeria do not consistently lead to

business success or sustainable growth. Achieving a certain level of education alone is not enough to acquire essential entrepreneurial competencies, such as problem-solving, financial literacy, and digital skills, which are crucial in the modern business environment (African Development Bank, 2019). Additionally, entrepreneurs' physical and emotional well-being, often overlooked, significantly impacts their ability to sustain business operations and foster creativity. Poor health outcomes can reduce productivity and hinder the long-term viability of businesses (World Health Organisation, 2021).

In Nigeria, there is a noticeable gap between the attributes of human capital and the requirements for effective entrepreneurial development. This gap is exacerbated by limited opportunities for training and development that do not adequately bridge the gap between education and practical entrepreneurial needs. Consequently, many aspiring entrepreneurs, despite their educational and training backgrounds, lack the necessary skills to navigate the complexities of the entrepreneurial landscape. Addressing these shortcomings in human capital development is vital to creating a more vibrant entrepreneurial ecosystem in Nigeria. Aligning education and training programs with the specific demands of the entrepreneurial sector is crucial to ensure that future entrepreneurs acquire the necessary skills. Moreover, improving access to healthcare services and promoting the welfare of entrepreneurs can enhance their productivity and resilience, positively affecting the performance of their businesses.

Statement of the Problem

The relationship between human capital and entrepreneurial development has been extensively studied in international economic literature, yet it remains underexplored within the context of Nigeria. Nigeria, with its youthful demographic and vast economic potential, faces significant challenges that hinder the full realisation of this relationship. High unemployment rates, especially among youth, and a high failure rate of newly established enterprises underscore the importance of developing a robust human capital framework to support entrepreneurship. Despite government efforts through initiatives like the Youth Entrepreneurship Support (YES) Programme and the National Youth Service Corps (NYSC) Skills Acquisition and Entrepreneurship Development (SAED) programme, the effectiveness of these initiatives is undermined by structural issues such as inadequate educational infrastructure, a disconnect between educational outcomes and market needs, limited access to continuous professional development, and poor health outcomes that impact workforce productivity. These issues highlight a gap between Nigeria's existing human capital characteristics and the requirements needed to promote effective entrepreneurial development.

Research has shown that entrepreneurs' educational background, work experience, and skills are vital to business success. However, in Nigeria, despite various training programmes, many entrepreneurs struggle to achieve sustainable growth. The lack of alignment between educational attainment and essential entrepreneurial competencies, such as financial literacy, problem-solving, and digital skills, hinders their ability to navigate the complex business environment. Furthermore, poor health can significantly affect entrepreneurs' productivity and the long-term sustainability of their ventures. These challenges call for a rethinking of human capital development strategies to ensure that educational programmes, skills development, and health services are aligned with the specific needs of the entrepreneurial sector.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study aims to investigate the relationship between human capital and entrepreneurial development across the three senatorial districts of Lagos State, Nigeria: Lagos Central, Lagos East, and Lagos West. The specific objectives are:

- i. To assess the impact of educational attainment on entrepreneurial development within the study area.
- ii. To examine the relationship between work experience and entrepreneurial development among individuals in the study area.
- iii. To analyse the influence of skills and competencies on entrepreneurial development in the study area.

Research Questions

Based on the study's aim and objectives, the following research questions are posed:

1. What is the impact of educational attainment on entrepreneurial development within the study area?
2. How does work experience influence entrepreneurial development among individuals in the study area?
3. What is the relationship between skills and competencies and entrepreneurial development in the study area?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses are tested in this study:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between educational attainment and entrepreneurial development in the study area.

H₀₂: Work experience has no significant effect on entrepreneurial development in the study area.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between skills and competencies and entrepreneurial development in the study area.

Significance of the Study

The study on "Human Capital and Entrepreneurial Development in Nigeria" provides critical insights and actionable recommendations to drive economic growth and diversification. Its findings are invaluable to policymakers, educational institutions, businesses, and aspiring entrepreneurs, offering a strategic framework to enhance entrepreneurial success and sustainable development. The study will contribute to filling the gap in understanding how human capital influences entrepreneurial development in Lagos State, providing evidence-based recommendations to improve human capital investment policies. This will ultimately contribute to fostering a more vibrant entrepreneurial ecosystem and enhancing Nigeria's economic resilience, particularly in light of the current challenges faced by the country.

Literature Review

Conceptual Review

This study investigates the relationship between human capital and entrepreneurial development, with a focus on Lagos State, Nigeria. Human capital, which includes education, work experience, skills, and health, is widely regarded as a crucial determinant of entrepreneurial success. As the foundation of innovation, economic growth, and productivity, human capital plays a pivotal role in entrepreneurial ventures by equipping individuals with the necessary knowledge and competencies to navigate challenges and seize opportunities.

Entrepreneurial Development

Entrepreneurial development involves activities and initiatives aimed at fostering the knowledge, skills, and mindset required to identify business opportunities and create new ventures. This encompasses entrepreneurial education, training, mentorship, access to financial resources, and the establishment of a supportive regulatory environment. Entrepreneurial development is central to stimulating economic growth, creating employment opportunities, and promoting innovation (Acs & Audretsch, 2010; Oyedokun, & Somoye, 2018a). It facilitates the creation of new firms while improving the efficiency and competitiveness of existing enterprises (Kuratko, 2016; Oyedokun, Awogbade, & Hassan, 2018).

At the individual level, entrepreneurial development includes the cultivation of an entrepreneurial mindset, including traits such as risk-taking, creativity, resilience, and strategic thinking. On a broader, systemic level, it involves fostering an ecosystem that supports entrepreneurship by ensuring access to capital, creating conducive policies, and encouraging a positive public attitude toward entrepreneurial activities. In Nigeria, the significance of entrepreneurship is underscored by the country's growing youth population and the need for economic diversification beyond the oil sector. The high unemployment rate further necessitates the promotion of entrepreneurship as a strategy for sustainable development (World Bank, 2020). However, Nigeria's entrepreneurial potential is stymied by challenges such as limited access to financial resources, inadequate infrastructure, and a lack of entrepreneurial education (Oyedokun & Somoye, 2018b National Bureau of Statistics, 2021).

Business Performance

Business performance is an essential indicator of success for entrepreneurs and a facet of entrepreneurial development. It encompasses various dimensions, including financial performance, market performance, operational efficiency, and inventive results. Standard indicators for evaluating business performance encompass revenue growth, profit generation capacity, market share acquisition, customer satisfaction levels, and the extent of product or service innovation (Venkatraman & Ramanujam, 1986). Financial performance is generally the clearest sign of corporate success, including metrics like sales, profit margins, and return on investment. These metrics illustrate the firm's ability to generate revenue, manage expenditures, and provide returns to stakeholders. Market performance, however, focusses on the company's market position, including its market share, customer base, and competitive advantage. Operational efficiency refers to a company's internal processes and its effectiveness in using resources. Conversely, innovation outcomes pertain to the organization's capacity to develop novel products, services, or processes (Murphy, Trailer, & Hill, 1996).

In Nigeria, business performance is influenced by various factors, including capital availability, market conditions, the regulatory framework, and the entrepreneur's skills and knowledge. The Nigerian business environment presents specific challenges, such as inadequate infrastructure, complex rules, and economic volatility, which can affect corporate performance (World Bank, 2020). Despite these challenges, significant opportunities for growth and innovation remain, particularly in sectors such as technology, agriculture, and services. Research indicates that multiple facets of human capital, such as educational attainment, professional experience, skills and competencies, health and wellness, and

training and development, significantly enhance company performance (Rauch & Rijsdijk, 2013). Entrepreneurs with higher education levels are often more skilled at managing complex business issues, innovating, and achieving increased growth rates. Davidsson and Honig (2003) assert that persons possessing pertinent work experience and advanced skills are more adept at navigating market challenges and sustaining a competitive advantage.

Business Survival and Sustainability

Business survival and sustainability are critical elements of entrepreneurial development that reflect a business's ability to endure and grow over time. Business survival refers to a company's capacity to endure initial challenges and maintain its operations beyond the early stages of its existence. Sustainability denotes a firm's ability to persist and prosper over time while adeptly adapting to market, environmental, and industry fluctuations (Wiklund & Shepherd, 2003). Survival and sustainability depend on several factors, including excellent financial management, strategic market positioning, optimal operational efficiency, and adaptability. Research indicates that organisations employing effective financial management practices, including proficient budgeting and cash flow oversight, are more likely to survive and thrive over the long term (Barney, 1991). Furthermore, organisations that pursue innovation and adapt their strategy to changing market conditions are more likely to exhibit enhanced sustainability. This is due to their superior ability to exploit fresh opportunities and alleviate any hazards (Hockerts, 2015). The challenges of sustaining and ensuring the long-term viability of firms in Nigeria are exacerbated by economic volatility, insufficient infrastructure, and regulatory impediments. Despite these challenges, opportunities exist for firms that can effectively leverage local resources, adapt to market changes, and implement sound management practices (World Bank, 2020).

Innovativeness and Creativity

Innovation and creativity are essential for entrepreneurial growth, facilitating the creation of new goods, services, and business models. Innovativeness refers to the ability to implement novel ideas and techniques that enhance organisational performance, whereas creativity involves the generation of original and valuable concepts that may lead to innovative solutions (Amabile, 1996). Comprehensive studies have consistently shown a robust association between elevated levels of innovation and creativity and the attainment of company success and expansion. Innovative organisations are better equipped to capture a greater market share, differentiate themselves from competitors, and respond to evolving consumer preferences (Schumpeter, 1934). Creativity, which precedes innovation, enables entrepreneurs to explore new opportunities and address difficulties from various perspectives, so strengthening their competitive advantage and ensuring enduring success (Runco & Jaeger, 2012). Establishing an environment that fosters creativity, and innovation is essential for advancing entrepreneurial development in Nigeria. However, challenges like as limited technological access, insufficient research and development infrastructure, and a lack of supportive policies may hinder the innovation process (National Bureau of Statistics, 2021). Overcoming these constraints is essential for enhancing the innovative capacity of Nigerian entrepreneurs.

Human Capital

Human capital includes the attributes gained by individuals via education, experience, skills, and health, which enhance their economic value and productivity. The concept is founded on economic theories that recognise the importance of investing in human resources for economic progress and innovation (Becker, 1964). Human capital theory posits that

investments in education, training, and health can augment an individual's production, resulting in favourable economic outcomes for society at large (Schultz, 1961; Oyedokun & Adeyemi, 2019). Human capital is crucial in the entrepreneurial context, affecting entrepreneurial ambitions, opportunity recognition, and total business success. It encompasses a diverse array of knowledge and competencies, including technical expertise, administrative ability, and interpersonal skills such as communication and leadership (Unger et al., 2011). Studies have shown that entrepreneurs with higher levels of human capital are more likely to identify viable business opportunities, secure financing, and effectively navigate the complexities of business management (Davidsson & Honig, 2003; Marvel et al., 2016).

The importance of human capital in entrepreneurial development is underscored in Nigeria due to the need for economic diversification and job creation, particularly in a rapidly growing and youthful demographic. The Nigerian economy's reliance on oil has highlighted the necessity for a highly skilled and adaptable workforce capable of fostering innovation and growth in sectors beyond oil (World Bank, 2020). Nonetheless, the advancement of human capital in Nigeria is hindered by challenges including inadequate educational infrastructure, a high rate of student dropouts, and a disconnect between the skills obtained through education and the requirements of the labour market (Oyedokun & Adeyemi, 2019; National Bureau of Statistics, 2021).

Education Level

The level of education, a fundamental component of human capital, plays a vital role in equipping individuals with the necessary knowledge and skills for participating in entrepreneurial endeavours. Comprehensive studies have been undertaken regarding the relationship between education and entrepreneurship. The findings consistently indicate that persons with elevated educational attainment exhibit greater intent and attain higher success in entrepreneurial ventures (Martin, McNally, & Kay, 2013). Education provides entrepreneurs with essential skills in critical thinking, financial literacy, and regulatory compliance, which are crucial for launching and sustaining a firm. The capacity of an entrepreneur to innovate and adjust to evolving market conditions can be significantly affected by their educational attainment. Postsecondary education often provides specialist knowledge and technical skills crucial for technology-driven enterprises. Moreover, education enhances an individual's ability to engage in strategic planning and management, hence increasing the likelihood of success in business (Kim et al., 2006). In Nigeria, there is a growing recognition of the need to improve access to high-quality education and align educational curriculum with the practical demands of the economy. Nonetheless, the inequitable allocation of educational resources and opportunities, particularly between urban and rural areas, poses significant challenges (UNESCO, 2020). Research in Nigeria indicates that entrepreneurs with higher education levels achieve better business outcomes, such as increased revenues and extended firm longevity (Adebayo et al., 2021). This advancement can be attributed to the comprehensive knowledge and cognitive skills acquired through formal education, which enhance entrepreneurial decision-making and creativity.

Work Experience

Work experience, as an element of human capital, refers to the knowledge and skills acquired via previous employment and professional engagements. It is essential for developing entrepreneurial skills, since it provides individuals with practical knowledge of industrial techniques, management, and operations. Dimov (2010) asserts that job experience enhances

an individual's ability to identify business opportunities, understand market dynamics, and navigate the complexities of business operations. Research indicates that prior professional experience, particularly in relevant sectors, is essential for the success of entrepreneurial ventures. Westhead, Ucbasaran, and Wright (2005) assert that entrepreneurs with experience in a specific domain are more likely to have a thorough understanding of client needs, supply chain management, and regulatory obligations. Moreover, obtaining managerial experience equips prospective entrepreneurs with vital leadership competencies and strategic thinking skills, which are crucial for the expansion and sustainability of a business (Parker, 2018). The acknowledgement of the impact of work experience on entrepreneurial results is increasing in Nigeria. However, the high unemployment rate and the lack of formal employment opportunities hinder the acquisition of essential work experience, particularly among youth (National Bureau of Statistics, 2021). The presence of this gap underscores the importance of alternative pathways, such as internships and apprenticeships, for gaining practical experience and enhancing entrepreneurial readiness.

Skills and Competencies

Skills and competences denote the particular technical abilities, cognitive skills, and personal attributes essential for the successful execution of tasks. In the field of entrepreneurship, these include skills in business administration, financial literacy, marketing proficiency, and problem-solving capabilities (Mitchelmore & Rowley, 2010). Acquiring these skills is essential for successfully creating and managing a firm. Entrepreneurs with strong skills and competences are more proficient at promoting innovation, adapting to changing market conditions, and efficiently managing business risks (Sánchez, 2013). Financial literacy enables entrepreneurs to make informed decisions regarding investing, budgeting, and financial planning, essential for securing the financial stability and growth of their enterprises. Marketing skills are advantageous for identifying and targeting specific audiences, building brand awareness, and increasing sales (Chell, 2013). The degree of entrepreneurial skills and competencies in Nigeria fluctuates significantly, influenced by factors such as educational quality, training accessibility, and socio-economic background. Despite the growing acknowledgement of the need of skill upgrading, many entrepreneurs still lack fundamental skills, hindering their business success and sustainability (Adebayo et al., 2021).

Theoretical Review

Various theories provide substantial insights into the relationship between human capital and entrepreneurial development. This examination evaluates two prominent theories: Human Capital Theory and the Resource-Based View (RBV). These concepts elucidate the influence of human capital investments on entrepreneurial achievement and corporate efficacy, particularly in Nigeria.

Human Capital Theory

Human Capital Theory, originally articulated by Gary Becker in 1964, asserts that investments in education, training, and experience enhance the productivity and economic value of humans. This concept is crucial for understanding the significance of human capital in promoting entrepreneurial growth. Advanced educational qualifications equip individuals with enhanced knowledge and skills essential for entrepreneurial success. Education augments cognitive abilities, problem-solving skills, and business insight, enabling

entrepreneurs to identify opportunities, reduce risks, and innovate effectively. Education in Nigeria is vital for equipping entrepreneurs with the ability to establish and sustain businesses amid economic challenges. Work experience is an essential component of human capital, providing practical knowledge and insights that are typically not acquired through formal education alone. Entrepreneurs with experience in analogous sectors obtain insights into market trends, develop operational competencies, and cultivate useful networks. Relevant job experience significantly enhances Nigerian entrepreneurs' capacity to comprehend and adjust to local market dynamics, therefore fostering the growth and sustainability of their enterprises.

Moreover, corporate performance is directly affected by specific skills and competencies, including financial management, strategic planning, and marketing. Entrepreneurs with strong skills are more likely to achieve greater business success, including profitability and market share. Targeted training initiatives in Nigeria can successfully mitigate skills deficiencies, resulting in enhanced entrepreneurial success and improved organisational performance. Health and well-being are essential components of human capital that influence entrepreneurial performance. The entrepreneur's ability to function effectively and make judicious decisions is augmented by excellent health, whereas poor health may impede productivity and increase the risk of business failure. Addressing health issues and promoting well-being in Nigeria enhances entrepreneurs' ability to sustain their operations and achieve lasting success. Training and development enhance human capital by increasing the skills and knowledge of entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurs may improve their adaptability to changing market conditions, foster innovation, and manage their businesses effectively through continuous learning and professional development. Improving access to high-quality training programs in Nigeria can foster entrepreneurial growth and substantially contribute to economic development.

Resource-Based View (RBV)

The Resource-Based View (RBV), created by Jay Barney in 1991, underscores the strategic importance of a firm's resources in achieving a competitive advantage. The Resource-Based View (RBV) asserts that human capital is a crucial strategic asset that can greatly enhance a corporation's sustainability and longevity. Entrepreneurs with substantial human capital resources, including specific skills and expertise, are better equipped to manage risks, respond to market fluctuations, and achieve sustained success. In Nigeria, leveraging human capital as a strategic asset can bolster organisational resilience and sustainability amid economic and infrastructural challenges. Within the Resource-Based View (RBV) framework, innovativeness and originality are considered significant assets. These resources enable organisations to develop unique products and services, distinguishing them from competitors and capturing a greater market share. Nigerian entrepreneurs can attain a competitive edge and foster business success by nurturing an innovative culture and augmenting their creative competencies.

The Resource-Based View emphasises the importance of access to critical resources, including financial capital, physical assets, and human resources, for achieving a competitive advantage. Entrepreneurs who can acquire and effectively employ these resources are more likely to attain success and expand their businesses. Improving access to resources, including

cash and infrastructure, is essential in Nigeria to foster entrepreneurial development and enhance corporate performance. The Resource-Based View (RBV) underscores the significance of entrepreneurial skills and competencies in the effective management and utilisation of strategic resources. Entrepreneurs with advanced skills are more adept at using their resources efficiently to achieve a competitive advantage and improve their organisation's success. Education and training in Nigeria can augment entrepreneurial capabilities, resulting in improved resource utilisation and heightened commercial performance. The interplay between human capital and entrepreneurial development can be elucidated through the synergistic perspectives of Human Capital Theory and the Resource-Based View. The Human Capital Theory emphasises the importance of education, work experience, skills, health, and training in enhancing entrepreneurial capability and corporate performance. The Resource-Based View underscores the strategic significance of human capital and other resources in achieving a competitive advantage and sustaining economic growth. These concepts collectively provide a comprehensive framework for understanding and addressing the challenges and opportunities within Nigeria's entrepreneurial landscape.

Review of Empirical Studies

Recent studies have concentrated significantly on the correlation between human capital and entrepreneurial advancement. This article analyses empirical research that explores the influence of education, work experience, skills and competencies, health and well-being, and training and development on entrepreneurial outcomes in Nigeria and other global contexts.

Education and Entrepreneurial Development

Education is universally acknowledged as a crucial element in cultivating entrepreneurial skills worldwide. A study by Rauch and Rijsdijk (2018) in the Netherlands demonstrated a positive association between higher education levels and entrepreneurial innovation and growth. The survey indicates that entrepreneurs with advanced education has superior skills in manoeuvring through complex business situations and capitalising on technological advancements. Unger et al. (2020) conducted a study in Southeast Asia, revealing that both formal and informal education significantly influenced entrepreneurial aspirations and the likelihood of venture success. The study emphasises the importance of the particular type and relevance of education for the business environment. Research by Afolabi et al. (2022) and Oni et al. (2021) in Nigeria demonstrates a positive link between higher education levels and enhanced business planning and decision-making skills. Mastery of these talents is essential for adeptly manoeuvring through market complexities and exploiting rising opportunities. Nonetheless, contemporary research frequently neglects to offer a comprehensive analysis of how varying levels and fields of education directly influence diverse facets of entrepreneurial success in Nigeria. This entails evaluating the differences in both the quality and quantity of education across different regions and sectors.

Work Experience and Business Performance

The influence of work experience on entrepreneurial development has been extensively studied worldwide. A study by Sarasvathy and Venkataraman (2019) in the United States shown that prior expertise in a particular industry significantly enhances an entrepreneur's ability to identify opportunities and effectively allocate resources. The study emphasised the

need of experiential learning and industry-specific knowledge for attaining success in business, particularly in high-tech and innovative fields. A study by Bosma et al. (2018) across various European countries revealed that acquiring employment experience in many fields fosters the development of cross-functional skills, which are advantageous for effectively managing and expanding a business. Research conducted by Adegboye and Adebayo (2021) and Ojo and Olugbemi (2023) in Nigeria indicates that possessing relevant industry expertise significantly enhances business success and sustainability. Seasoned entrepreneurs in their respective domains typically have a profound comprehension of resource allocation and market dynamics, crucial for attaining sustained economic prosperity. The literature often neglects to address the specific types of work experience that are most beneficial for entrepreneurs across various sectors and regions in Nigeria, along with the duration and quality of such experience.

Skills and Competencies in Business Performance

Competence and talents are essential for entrepreneurial success in a global context. A study by Khan and Aslam (2021) in Pakistan shown a strong correlation between entrepreneurial skills, including financial literacy and marketing expertise, and the attainment of business goals. The study highlighted the importance of both technical and interpersonal skills in achieving sustainable business growth. A study by Audretsch et al. (2020) in Canada highlighted the importance of entrepreneurial competencies in fostering innovation and resilience, particularly during economic downturns. The significance of skills and competencies in enhancing corporate performance in Nigeria is widely acknowledged. Research by Alabi et al. (2022) and Ibrahim and Salisu (2020) underscores the importance of essential competencies, including financial management and strategic planning, in achieving a competitive advantage. Nevertheless, these studies generally do not differentiate between the impacts of soft skills, like leadership and communication, and hard skills, such as technical proficiency. Moreover, there is a scarcity of longitudinal studies that assess the influence of skill development on business performance and growth in Nigeria.

Figure 2.1: Conceptual Model

Source: Researchers' Compilation, 2024

Figure 2.1 illustrates the correlation between the independent variable of human capital and the dependent variable of entrepreneurial development. This conceptual framework was established following a comprehensive literature review. It demonstrates how changes in one variable can influence the other. The approach assesses human capital by evaluating criteria such as education level, work experience, and skills and competencies. Entrepreneurial development is assessed by analysing characteristics such as business performance, business survival and sustainability, as well as innovativeness and creativity.

Summary of Gaps in Literature

Empirical investigations reveal substantial gaps in the current literature about human capital and entrepreneurial development in Lagos State, Nigeria. Although current research demonstrates a positive correlation between educational attainment and entrepreneurial success (Afolabi et al., 2022; Oni et al., 2021), there is a lack of thorough investigation into the specific impact of various degrees and fields of study on different aspects of entrepreneurial achievement. The correlation between the quality and quantity of education and its influence on entrepreneurial outcomes across different areas and sectors in Nigeria remains inadequately explored (Oni et al., 2021). Regarding work experience, while research by Adegboye and Adebayo (2021) and Ojo and Olugbemi (2023) highlights its positive influence on business performance and sustainability, they often neglect to specify the particular types of work experience that provide the most advantages. Additional research is necessary to assess the influence of the duration and quality of work experience on entrepreneurial success across different sectors and regions in Nigeria (Adegboye & Adebayo, 2021).

Research by Alabi et al. (2022) and Ibrahim and Salisu (2020) indicates that skills and competencies are essential for improving company success. Nevertheless, these studies generally do not differentiate between the effects of soft skills (e.g., leadership) and hard skills (e.g., technical proficiency). Moreover, there is a scarcity of longitudinal studies that assess the influence of skill development on business performance and growth over an extended duration (Ibrahim & Salisu, 2020). Hassan and Ali (2021) and Okafor et al. (2022) have underscored the significance of optimal health and well-being in attaining entrepreneurial success. Nonetheless, the current literature often neglects to comprehensively analyse the particular impact of various health aspects, such as mental health compared to physical health, on different entrepreneurial endeavours. Moreover, there is an insufficient body of research concerning the effectiveness of health treatments in improving entrepreneurial outcomes in Nigeria (Hassan & Ali, 2021).

Despite the findings of Oyeleke et al. (2022) and Eze and Okoro (2023) regarding the positive influence of training and development on business success, there is still insufficient understanding of the specific types of training that produce the greatest efficacy. Further research is necessary to evaluate the long-term impacts of various training programs and determine how certain training methodologies address the unique needs of entrepreneurs across multiple regions in Nigeria (Eze & Okoro, 2023). Addressing these gaps will enhance understanding of how human capital determinants influence entrepreneurial performance in Nigeria, hence informing the formulation of more effective policies and initiatives.

Methodology

Research Design

This research employed a descriptive cross-sectional methodology to examine the relationship between human capital and entrepreneurial development in Lagos State, Nigeria. This approach facilitates the collection of extensive data on current entrepreneurial activities and human capital factors within specific Local Government Areas (LGAs) during a defined period.

Population and Sampling

The research investigates entrepreneurs functioning in three senatorial districts of Lagos State, Nigeria: Lagos Central, Lagos East, and Lagos West. According to the 2022 National MSME Survey done by the National Bureau of Statistics, Nigeria comprises 41 million micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs). Additionally, the Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN) reports that there are 670,447 small and medium-sized firms (SMEs) in Nigeria. Of them, 42,067 are located in Lagos State, constituting around 6.3% of the total number of SMEs (SMEDAN, 2021). A sample of 1,500 entrepreneurs was selected using stratified random sampling to correctly represent the population. This entailed segmenting the population into various groups according to the Local Government Areas (LGAs), followed by the selection of persons from each group to ensure equitable representation of diverse firm sectors and sizes. The sample size was determined utilising Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) table for estimating the necessary sample size.

Pilot Study

A pilot research was conducted in five designated administrative divisions of Ibadan: Oluyole, Ibadan South East, Ibadan South West, Ibadan North, and Ido, encompassing a total of 150 SMEs. The aim was to evaluate the clarity, feasibility, and reliability of the research instruments. The preliminary study demonstrated a reliability coefficient of 0.83, indicating strong internal consistency and stability (Field, 2018).

Description of the Research Instrument

The main instrument employed for data collection in this study is a meticulously crafted questionnaire aimed to obtain comprehensive information regarding human capital attributes and their impact on entrepreneurial growth. The survey comprises both closed and open-ended enquiries. Closed-ended questions utilise Likert scales for quantitative assessment, whereas open-ended questions provide qualitative insights.

Data Collection

Data collection utilised both conventional and digital methods to accommodate participant choices. The data collection phase spanned four weeks, allowing ample time for obtaining responses and performing follow-ups, which yielded a high response rate. Strict confidentiality was implemented to ensure accurate and truthful responses.

Data Analysis

The data analysis utilised version 20.0 of the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). Descriptive statistics, including means, frequencies, and standard deviations, were employed to summarise the data. Regression analysis, a form of inferential statistics, was employed to examine the relationships between human capital attributes and entrepreneurial growth results.

Results and Discussion of Findings

Demographic Data Analysis

The sample consisted of 1,500 small and medium-sized enterprises, chosen to accurately represent the population distribution across the three senatorial districts of Lagos State in Nigeria: Lagos Central, Lagos East, and Lagos West. A complete and equitable demographic representation was therefore assured.

Table 1: Analysis of Variables

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	1394	92.9
Female	106	7.1
Age bracket		
21- 30	131	8.7
31- 40	379	25.3
41- 50	632	42.1
51- 60	192	12.8
61- 65	166	11.1
Educational attainment		
ND/NCE	104	6.9
Bachelor's Degree/HND	748	49.9
PGD/Master's Degree	567	37.8
M.Phil.	32	2.1
Ph.D.	30	2.0
Others	19	1.3
Job level		
Top management	188	12.5
Middle management	1057	70.5
Operational management	255	17.0
Length of service		
Below 5yrs	188	12.5
6-10yrs	900	60.0
11-15yrs	334	22.3
16yrs +	78	5.2

Source: Researchers' Compilation, 2024

Analysis of Variables

Table 1 illustrates that 92.9% of respondents are male (n=1394), whilst 7.1% are female (n=106), demonstrating a pronounced male predominance in the sample. The predominant age group among respondents is 41-50 years, comprising 42.1% (n=632). The second highest age cohort is 31-40 years, accounting for 25.3% (n=379). Lower percentages are observed in the 51-60 years range (12.8%, n=192), 61-65 years (11.1%, n=166), and the 21-30 years

range (8.7%, n=131). Concerning educational qualifications, almost half of the participants (49.9%, n=748) own a Bachelor's degree or Higher National Diploma, while 37.8% (n=567) hold a Postgraduate Diploma or Master's degree. A minority of respondents possess ND/NCE (6.9%, n=104), M.Phil. (2.1%, n=32), or Ph.D. (2.0%, n=30), while 1.3% (n=19) fall into the "Others" group. The majority of respondents, 70.5% (n=1057), in middle management positions, followed by 17.0% (n=255) in operational management, and 12.5% (n=188) in top management. Regarding length of service, 60.0% (n=900) of respondents possess 6-10 years of experience, whereas 22.3% (n=334) have 11-15 years of tenure. A minor segment possesses less than 5 years of employment (12.5%, n=188), while merely 5.2% (n=78) have been employed for over 16 years. The findings indicate a workforce predominantly composed of middle-aged, highly educated males in middle management positions, with the majority of respondents possessing substantial experience in their current employment.

Presentation of Data

Table 2: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.088 ^a	.008	.007	13.61060	.008	11.796	1	1498	.001
2	.966 ^b	.934	.934	3.51317	.926	20986.718	1	1497	.000
3	.970 ^c	.941	.941	3.32142	.007	178.838	1	1496	.000

- a. Predictors: (Constant), EducationLevel
- b. Predictors: (Constant), EducationLevel, WorkExperience
- c. Predictors: (Constant), EducationLevel, WorkExperience, SkillsandCompetencies

The hierarchical regression model presented in Table 2 analyses the correlation between human capital and entrepreneurial development in Lagos State, Nigeria. In Model 1, education level alone explains a minor fraction of the variance in entrepreneurial development, with a R value of 0.088, signifying a weak association. The R² value of 0.008 indicates that merely 0.8% of the variance in entrepreneurial development is attributable to education level. The model demonstrates statistical significance with a F change of 11.796 and a p-value of 0.001, indicating that education level exerts a little yet statistically significant influence. In Model 2, the inclusion of job experience markedly enhances the model's performance. The R value rises to 0.966, signifying a robust association. The R² value increases to 0.934, indicating that 93.4% of the variance in entrepreneurial development is now accounted for by the interplay of education level and work experience. The considerable F change (20986.718) and the very significant p-value (0.000) underscore the important influence of work experience on entrepreneurial development.

In Model 3, the incorporation of abilities and competences enhances the model, resulting in a R value of 0.970. The R² value is currently 0.941, indicating that 94.1% of the variance in entrepreneurial development is accounted for by the combined factors of education level, work experience, and skills and competencies. The alteration in R² (0.007) and the F change (178.838) are statistically significant (p-value = 0.000), indicating that abilities and

competences, albeit a lesser increment relative to job experience, nevertheless provide substantial contributions to the model. In conclusion, educational attainment exerts a modest although notable influence on entrepreneurial development, whereas work experience substantially amplifies the model's predictive capacity, and the incorporation of skills and competencies contributes additional value. Human capital considerations combined account for a substantial share of the variance in entrepreneurial development in Lagos State.

Test for Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between educational attainment and entrepreneurial development in the study area.

This was tested using Hierarchical Multiple Regression (HMR) and the test result is presented on Table 2.

Test for Hypothesis 1

To evaluate Hypothesis 1, which investigates the correlation between education level and entrepreneurial development, the researchers utilise the model summary outcomes from the hierarchical regression analysis. In Model 1, the R value of 0.088 indicates a weak positive association between educational attainment and entrepreneurial development. The R² score of 0.008 signifies that merely 0.8% of the variance in entrepreneurial development is accounted for by education level alone. This indicates that although education has an impact, it does not substantially explain the majority of the variance in entrepreneurial success. The F-statistic is 11.796, accompanied with a p-value of 0.001, indicating statistical significance ($p < 0.05$). The researchers dismiss the null hypothesis (H₀₁) and endorse the alternative hypothesis, indicating that a significant association exists between education level and entrepreneurial development in the study area, albeit with a relatively small impact size. In conclusion, educational attainment has a substantial role in entrepreneurial development, while its total influence remains moderate.

Hypothesis 2

H₀₂: Work experience has no significant effect on entrepreneurial development in the study area.

This was tested using Hierarchical Multiple Regression (HMR) and the test result is presented on Table 2.

Test for Hypothesis 2

To evaluate Hypothesis 2, which investigates the correlation between work experience and entrepreneurial development, the researchers analyse the outcomes from Model 2 of the hierarchical regression. An R value of 0.966 suggests a robust positive association between education level, work experience, and entrepreneurial development. An R² value of 0.934 indicates that 93.4% of the variance in entrepreneurial development is accounted for by the combined effects of education level and work experience, with work experience playing a considerable role in this relationship. The R² change of 0.926 indicates that incorporating work experience into the model enhanced the explained variance by 92.6%, highlighting its significant impact on entrepreneurial development. The F-statistic is 20,986.718, accompanied with a p-value of 0.000, indicating statistical significance ($p < 0.05$). Consequently, the researchers dismiss the null hypothesis (H₀₂) and endorse the alternative

hypothesis (H₁₂), determining that a strong association exists between work experience and entrepreneurial development in the study area. In conclusion, work experience has a considerable and notable favourable influence on entrepreneurial development, surpassing the impact of school level alone.

Hypothesis 3

Ho3: There is no significant relationship between skills and competencies and entrepreneurial development in the study area.

This was tested using Hierarchical Multiple Regression (HMR) and the test result is presented on Table 2.

Test for Hypothesis 3

To evaluate Hypothesis 3, which investigates the correlation between skills and competencies and entrepreneurial development, the researchers analyse the outcomes from Model 3 of the hierarchical regression. An R value of 0.970 indicates a robust positive association among education level, work experience, skills and competencies, and entrepreneurial development. The R² value of 0.941 signifies that 94.1% of the variance in entrepreneurial growth is accounted for by the collective influence of these three factors. The R² change of 0.007 signifies that the incorporation of abilities and competencies into the model added an extra 0.7% to the explained variance, demonstrating that although its contribution is statistically significant, its additional effect is rather minor relative to work experience. The F-statistic is 178.838, accompanied with a p-value of 0.000, indicating that the link is statistically significant (p < 0.05). The academics reject the null hypothesis (Ho3) and accept the alternative hypothesis, indicating that a strong association exists between skills and competencies and entrepreneurial development in the studied area. In conclusion, although skills and competencies substantially influence entrepreneurial development, their effect is less pronounced than that of education level and work experience.

Table 3: ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	2185.267	1	2185.267	11.796	.001 ^b
	Residual	277502.287	1498	185.249		
	Total	279687.554	1499			
2	Regression	261211.032	2	130605.516	10581.886	.000 ^c
	Residual	18476.522	1497	12.342		
	Total	279687.554	1499			
3	Regression	263183.946	3	87727.982	7952.265	.000 ^d
	Residual	16503.608	1496	11.032		
	Total	279687.554	1499			

a. Dependent Variable: EntrepreneurialDevelopment

b. Predictors: (Constant), EducationLevel

c. Predictors: (Constant), EducationLevel, WorkExperience

d. Predictors: (Constant), EducationLevel, WorkExperience, SkillsandCompetencies

In Model 1, as shown in Table 3, the regression sum of squares is 2185.267, signifying the variation in entrepreneurial development solely attributable to Education Level. The model exhibits statistical significance with an F-value of 11.796 and a p-value of 0.001, indicating that education level has a significant, though moderate, impact on entrepreneurial development. The residual sum of squares (277502.287) signifies the unexplained variance in entrepreneurial development by the model, resulting in a mean square error of 185.249. In Model 2, the incorporation of work experience as a predictor markedly increases the regression sum of squares to 261211.032, signifying a considerably larger proportion of variance explained by the model. The F-value of 10581.886 ($p = 0.000$) indicates that the model, which includes education level and work experience, is statistically significant. The residual sum of squares (18476.522) is significantly reduced, with a mean square error of 12.342, suggesting that the inclusion of work experience greatly improves the model's explanatory power. Model 3, by integrating Skills and Competencies, increases the regression sum of squares to 263183.946, signifying a further improvement in the explained variance. The F-value (7952.265) is extremely significant ($p = 0.000$), with the residual sum of squares decreasing to 16503.608, resulting in a mean square error of 11.032. This indicates that while the integration of skills and competencies augments the model, the degree of enhancement is less substantial than that of work experience.

In essence, educational achievement constitutes only a small portion of the heterogeneity in entrepreneurial development. The inclusion of work experience significantly improves the model, whereas the integration of skills and competencies refines its prediction power, though to a smaller extent. Each predictor significantly contributes to clarifying the variance in entrepreneurial development, as demonstrated by the decreasing residual sum of squares across the models.

Table 4: Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error				Beta	Lower Bound
1	(Constant)	59.316	1.312		45.202	.000	56.742	61.890
	EducationLevel	.185	.054	.088	3.435	.001	.079	.291
2	(Constant)	-8.744	.579		-15.097	.000	-9.880	-7.608
	EducationLevel	.292	.014	.140	20.971	.000	.265	.319
	WorkExperience	3.034	.021	.964	144.868	.000	2.993	3.075
3	(Constant)	-5.979	.585		-10.214	.000	-7.127	-4.830
	EducationLevel	.190	.015	.091	12.516	.000	.161	.220
	WorkExperience	2.615	.037	.831	70.562	.000	2.542	2.688
	SkillsandCompetencies	.398	.030	.163	13.373	.000	.340	.456

a. Dependent Variable: EntrepreneurialDevelopment

The results presented in Table 4 indicate that the hierarchical regression analysis underscores the influence of education level, work experience, and skills and competencies on entrepreneurial development. The following is the analysis of the three models:

Model 1: The unstandardised coefficient for the constant is $B = 59.316$, which means that when the education level is zero, the entrepreneurial development score is 59.316. The coefficient for education level is $B = 0.185$ with a t-value of 3.435 ($p = 0.001$), signifying a statistically significant positive correlation between education level and entrepreneurial development. The standardised beta coefficient is 0.088, indicating that education level accounts for 8.8% of the variance in entrepreneurial development. The confidence interval for education level (0.079, 0.291) indicates a positive and statistically significant effect.

Model 2: Incorporating work experience into the model results in a constant of $B = -8.744$, with a t-value of -15.097 ($p = 0.000$), signifying that in the absence of education and work experience, entrepreneurial development is adversely affected. The impact of education level rises somewhat to $B = 0.292$, with a standardised beta of 0.140, indicating that education level accounts for 14% of the variance. Work experience has a substantial and considerable positive influence on entrepreneurial growth, evidenced by a coefficient of $B = 3.034$ and a standardised beta of 0.964, indicating that work experience accounts for 96.4% of the variance in entrepreneurial development. The t-value for job experience is 144.868 ($p = 0.000$), establishing it as the most significant predictor in the model.

Model 3: The inclusion of skills and competencies results in a constant of $B = -5.979$ ($p = 0.000$), whereas the coefficient for education level marginally decreases to $B = 0.190$, with a beta of 0.091. The impact of work experience diminishes to $B = 2.615$ with a beta of 0.831, however it continues to be a very significant predictor. Skills and competencies strongly influence entrepreneurial development, with a coefficient of $B = 0.398$ and a standardised beta of 0.163, indicating that they account for 16.3% of the variance in entrepreneurial development. The t-value for abilities and competencies is 13.373 ($p = 0.000$), indicating a significant effect.

The coefficients indicate that work experience exerts the most substantial influence on entrepreneurial development, succeeded by skills and competencies, and subsequently education level, with all factors demonstrating statistically significant impacts.

4.3 Discussion of Findings

Model 1 demonstrates that education level exerts a strong positive influence on entrepreneurial development; however, the effect is modest, as evidenced by a R^2 of 0.008, signifying that education level accounts for merely 0.8% of the variance in entrepreneurial growth. The ANOVA results validate the statistical significance of this model ($F = 11.796$, $p = 0.001$). This indicates that although education is significant, it is not the exclusive factor in achieving entrepreneurial success. In Model 2, the inclusion of work experience in conjunction with education significantly enhances the model's explanatory ability. The R^2 rises to 0.934, indicating that 93.4% of the variance in entrepreneurial development is accounted for by education and work experience. The ANOVA indicates that this model is extremely significant ($F = 10581.886$, $p < 0.001$). The coefficients indicate that work experience exerts a significant and positive influence on entrepreneurial development ($B =$

3.034, $t = 144.868$, $p = 0.000$), underscoring the essential importance of practical experience in promoting entrepreneurial success.

In Model 3, the incorporation of skills and competencies enhances the model, resulting in a R^2 of 0.941, signifying that education, work experience, and skills collectively account for 94.1% of the variance in entrepreneurial development. The ANOVA validates the model's significance ($F = 7952.265$, $p = 0.000$). The findings indicate that, although work experience is the most robust predictor, abilities and competencies also exert a considerable positive influence ($B = 0.398$, $t = 13.373$, $p = 0.000$). This underscores the significance of possessing the appropriate skill set and competencies, alongside education and experience, for entrepreneurial advancement. The findings indicate that although education is fundamental, practical work experience and particular skills and competencies exert a far greater impact on entrepreneurial success. The integration of these three elements establishes a strong foundation for promoting entrepreneurial growth in Lagos State.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The research examined the correlation between human capital elements - education level, work experience, and skills and competencies - and entrepreneurial development in Lagos State, employing hierarchical regression analysis. Model 1 revealed a modest although significant correlation between education level and entrepreneurial development, with $R^2 = 0.008$, indicating that education accounted for 0.8% of the variance in entrepreneurial development. The F-statistic (11.796, $p = 0.001$) validated that this association was statistically significant, hence rejecting the null hypothesis. In Model 2, the incorporation of work experience in conjunction with schooling markedly enhanced the model's explanatory capacity, resulting in a R^2 of 0.934. Education and work experience account for 93.4% of the variance in entrepreneurial development. The F-statistic (20,986.718, $p = 0.000$) indicated a substantial correlation, resulting in the rejection of the second null hypothesis. In Model 3, the incorporation of abilities and competencies elevated the explained variance to 94.1% ($R^2 = 0.941$). The F-statistic (178.838, $p = 0.000$) indicated that skills and competencies significantly positively influenced entrepreneurial development, while their incremental contribution was comparatively minor relative to work experience.

The coefficient analysis indicated that work experience exerted the most significant influence on entrepreneurial development ($\beta = 0.831$), succeeded by skills and competencies ($\beta = 0.163$), and education level ($\beta = 0.091$). All variables exhibited statistical significance, with p-values substantially below 0.05. In conclusion, the results demonstrate that although education is significant, work experience, skills, and competencies are far more influential in fostering entrepreneurial development in Lagos State.

The hierarchical regression analysis indicates that human capital factors, including education level, work experience, and skills and competencies, significantly influence entrepreneurial development in Lagos State. The findings indicate that although education correlates positively with entrepreneurial development, its influence is minimal relative to other criteria such as work experience and abilities. Work experience proved to be a significant determinant, accounting for a considerable share of the variance in entrepreneurial results, suggesting that individuals with extensive practical experience are more adept at managing the intricacies of entrepreneurship. Likewise, skills and competencies were identified as key contributors to entrepreneurial success, underscoring the relevance of practical and technical ability in promoting sustainable business endeavours. The research highlights that, while

formal education is crucial, its independent impact on entrepreneurship is restricted. The amalgamation of pertinent experience and gained abilities offers a more robust basis for entrepreneurial advancement. The findings indicate that policies and initiatives designed to foster entrepreneurship should emphasise the cultivation of practical skills and experiential learning, alongside improving educational options. By doing so, entrepreneurial projects are more likely to thrive and significantly contribute to the overall economic development of Lagos State and beyond.

This study presents the following proposals to improve entrepreneurial growth in Lagos State:

1. Promote experiential learning: Entrepreneurs ought to engage in real work settings to get pertinent experience, which substantially enhances entrepreneurial success.
2. Establish skill-based training programmes: Policymakers should prioritise the creation of training centres that cultivate vital entrepreneurial skills and capabilities, extending beyond formal schooling.
3. Augment educational curricula: Educational institutions ought to incorporate entrepreneurship-focused courses that prioritise practical business competencies in conjunction with theoretical understanding.
4. Foster mentorship and apprenticeship programmes: The government and commercial sectors should combine to offer mentorship opportunities enabling aspiring entrepreneurs to learn directly from seasoned business owners.
5. Encourage ongoing professional development: Entrepreneurs must be motivated to consistently enhance their abilities, as growing competencies are essential for maintaining competitiveness in dynamic marketplaces.

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